

CURRICULAM VITAE of Prof.Ramesh

NAME : Dr. Ramesh
Religion : Hindu
Designation : Professor of Law and Dean Faculty of Law
Qualification : B.A., LL.M., Ph.D.
Area of specialisation : Constitutional Law, Administrative Law and Research Methodology
Teaching Experience : 25years

Address for correspondence:

Professor of law
DOS in Law, University of Mysore,
Manasagangotri.
Mysore

Subject Taught:

1. Constitutional Law
2. Administrative Law
3. Karnataka Land Revenue Act
4. Rent Control Act, Land Reforms Act, Land Acquisition Act, Registration Act,
5. Criminology
6. Contract
7. Environment Law
8. Jurisprudence
9. Interpretation of Statute
10. Intellectual Property Laws.
11. World Trade Law
12. Information Technology Law
13. Right to information Act, 2005
14. Women and Law
15. Feminist Jurisprudence
16. Law on Human Rights and duties

Obtained Ph.D. in Constitutional Law

Educational Career

Name of the Examination Passed	School or college or institution from which passed	Month and year of passing	Name of the University Board	Class obtained & Percentage	Subject offered principal, voluntary or subsidiary
B.A.,	University Evening college, Mysore.	October 1984	University of Mysore	Pass class 40%	Kannada, Eng Economics, Political Science, Sociology
LL.B.,	Sarada vilas Law College, Mysore.	October 1989	University of Mysore	Pass class 49%	Compulsory Subjects prescribed by the University
LL.M.,	University of Mysore	April 1993	University of Mysore	Second class 59%	Jurisprudence Constitutional & Admv. Law, Jurisprudence
Ph.D.	University of Mysore	August 2003	University of Mysore	-----	A Critical study of the System and working of PRI with Special reference to the Mysore district of Karnataka State.

Administrative Experiences:

1. Served as Professor cum director, centre for the study of social exclusion and Inclusive Policy, from May 2010 to March 2014.
2. Served as Chairman of Department of Studies in law, and Director of School of law, University of Mysore, Mysore, from 2016-2018

Details of Services

SL No	Name of the Institution	Designation	Period From	To	Pay Drawn	Temporary/ Permanent
1	R.L Law College, Belgaum	Lecturer in Law	27-1-1995	15-6-1999	As per the state Government Scale	Permanent
2	University college of Law Dharawad (A constituent college of Karnataka University)	Lecturer in Law	15-6-1999	26-1-2001	As per U.G.C pay scales	Permanent
3	- DO-	Lecturer in law (Senior Scale)	26-1-2001	1 st April 2007	As per U.G.C pay scales	Permanent
4	University of Mysore	Reader in law	3 rd April 2007	5 th May 2010	As per U.G.C. Pay scales	Permanent
5	University of Mysore	Associate Professor	3 rd April, 2010	4 th May 2010	As per UGC Pay scale	Permanent
5	University of Mysore	Professor cum Director, Centre for the study of Social exclusion and Inclusive Policy	6 th May 2010	28-2-2015	As per UGC pay Scales	Permanent
5	University of Mysore	Associate Professor	1 st March, 2015	Till date	As per UGC Pay scales	permanent

Teaching and other Assignments

1. Teaching in the Mysore University School of Justice (A constituent College of University of Mysore, Mysore) for the past three years.

2. Further I am also teaching at centre for the women studies, University of Mysore, Mysore.
3. Visiting faculty to Academic staff College, University of Mysore, Mysore.
4. M.Phil Degree in area studies (under UPE)
5. Furthermore, I had the opportunity of serving the University of Mysore, Mysore for 14 years as Second Division Clerk.

PRESENTATION OF PAPERS IN SEMINARS, WORKSHOPS & SYMPOSIUMS

1. Presented a paper entitled “*Constitution of India: Dr. Ambedkar Perspective*” at the *workshop* conducted by the *Department of Dr. Ambedkar Studies*, Karnataka University Dharwad on 13th March 2000.
2. Presented a paper entitled “*Educational Rights of Minorities in India*” at the symposium conducted by the *Department of Studies in Law*, Karnataka University, Dharwad on 6th October 2003.
3. Presented a paper at the *National Seminar* on “*By Laws for Implementation of Environmental Friendly Projects*” sponsored by AICTE New Delhi Organized by *Department of Civil Engineering, JSS’s K.H.Kabur Institute of Engineering Dharwad* at Balakundry Bhavan, Institution of Engineers, Dharwad on 18th July 2004 and presented a paper on “*Environmental Issues*”.
4. Presented a paper in the *Two Day State level seminar* on “*Perspectives in Intellectual Property Rights*” sponsored by Ministry of Human Resource Development Delhi, and organized by J.S.S Law College, Hubli, and Karnataka and presented a paper on “*Criteria for Registrability of Industrial Designs*” on 13th and 14th August 2005.
5. Presented a paper in *Two day National Level workshop* on “*Intellectual Property Rights*” sponsored by the Ministry of Human Resource Development, Delhi, and organized by Siddhartha Law College, Gulbarga, Karnataka, and presented a paper on “*Intellectual Property Rights*” on 23rd October 2005.
6. Presented a paper at the *National Seminar* held on 11th and 12th March 2006 on the topic “*Development of Constitutional Law in India through the Judicial Process*” Organized by Pendekanti Law College, Hyderabad, Andhra Pradesh.
7. Presented a paper at the *National Seminar* held on 25th and 26th March 2006 on the topic “*The problems of law making in the federal polity*” Organized by Vidhya Vardhak Law College, Mysore.
8. Presented a paper at the **State level seminar** on the topic “***Working of right to information Act 2005***”, conducted by KLE Societies Law College, Chikodi, on 24th September 2006.
9. Presented a paper at the **National level workshop** on “***Women’s Right***”, jointly organised by National human right commission, New Delhi and university college of law, PG *Department of Law*, Karnataka University, Dharwad, held on 14th and 15th October 2006.
10. Presented a paper in the 6th Sociological conference on the topic “***Women in Indian politics-A critique***” Conducted by P.G.Department of Studies in Sociology, Karnataka University, Dharwad, on 28th to 30th October 2006.

11. Presented a paper in the **National Seminar** on the topic “**Judicial Inquire Bill 2006**” Conducted by Department of Law, University of Kerala, Trivandrum, on 25th and 26th October 2007.
12. Presented a paper at the **National level seminar** on the topic “**Industrial Designs and Laws**” conducted by the Vidhyavardhaka Law College, Mysore, on 26th and 27th May 2007.
13. Presented a paper at the **National Level Seminar** on the topic “**SEZ visa-visa. Human Rights**” Conducted by SDM Law College, Mangalore. On 16th December 2007.
14. Presented a paper on at the **National level seminar**, on the topic “**Study of Constitutional provisions in the light of report of HPC to study the regional imbalance in Karnataka**” Conducted by SCAB Law College, Raichur, on 9th February 2008.
15. Presented a paper on the **National Seminar** on the topic “**Place of women in the Human Rights**” Conducted by Dr. B. R. Ambedkar Research and Extension Centre, Manasagangotri, University of Mysore, Mysore, on 18th March 2008.
16. Presented a paper in the **National workshop on the topic “Social Security of the aged – Problems and Perspectives**” Conducted by the Department of Studies in Law, Manasagangotri, University of Mysore, Mysore, on 29th March 2008.
17. Presented a paper entitled “**Obscenity and Pornography: a critique**” at one day **national seminar on “Cyber Crimes and Human Rights: New Perspective**” conducted by Centre for Information Science and Technology” (CIST), Manasagangotri, University of Mysore, Mysore on 2nd February 2009.
18. Presented a paper entitled “**Dalits and Conversion**” at one day **National Seminar** on “Constitutional Status of Religious Conversion” Organised by Department of Studies in Law, Manasagangotri, University of Mysore, Mysore, on 26th February, 2009 .
19. Presented a Paper Entitled “**Religion and Caste: a Base for social exclusion**” at two day **National Seminar** on “Culture of Social Exclusion, Identities and Inclusive Policy: Daliths, Minorities and Tribes, India/ Karnataka” Organized by Centre for the Study of Social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy and Department in Political Science, History and Sociology, Mnasagangotri, University of Mysore, Mysore. On 11th and 12th March 2009.
20. Presented a paper entitled “**Fundamental Aspects of Good Governance: A Critique**” at two day National Seminar on Good Governance- its Dimensions and Challenges Organized by the Vivekananda College of Law, Bangalore, on 26th and 27th March 2010.
21. Presented a paper on the topic “ **Status of De-notified Tribes in Karnataka**” at the National Conference jointly conducted by the Centre for the Study of Social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy, University of Mysore, and Department of Studies in History, University of Mysore, Mysore on 23rd and 24th December, 2010. The thrust area of this conference was “ Ethno-Historical Development of De-notified Tribes (DNTs): Issues and Prospects.

22. Presented a poster on the paper entitled “**International money laundering and terrorist financing : a critical overview**” at the sixth international multidisciplinary conference conducted jointly by UGC academic staff college, university of Mysore, Mysore, ministry of science research & technology, and union of Iranian students Islamic association from 14th and 15th January 2011.
23. Presented a paper entitled “**Protection of women at working places**” at two day National Seminar on women and work: policies towards economic inclusion, Organized by the centre for women’s studies and centre for the study of social exclusion and inclusive policy, university of Mysore, Mysore, held on 21st and 22nd March 2011.
24. Presented a paper at the prelude conference conducted by Dr. B. R. Ambedkar Research and Extension centre on the Topic “**Dalit Development and Inclusive Growth-Issues and Prospects**” on 28th March 2011.
25. Presented a paper in the two day **National Conference** on “Decentralized Governance and Rural Development” organised by Institute of Development Studies, University of Mysore, Mysore, held on 13- 14th May 2011. The title of the paper was “**impact of some legislation on Panchayat governance**”.
26. Presented a paper in the UGC sponsored two day **National Seminar on Modern Trends in Historiography**” organized by Post Graduate and Research Department of History Nirmala College for Women (Autonomous) Coimbatore (in collaboration with Department of History Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirapally held on 28th and 29th July 2011. The title of the paper is “**Impact of Marxism on Legal theory- an analysis**”.
27. Presented a paper entitled “**Is public health a fundamental right?**” at two day National conference on **multilevel interventions for health care: framing new inclusive health policies**, Organized by centre for the study of social exclusion and inclusive policy, university of Mysore, Mysore, held on September 8th and 9th 2011.
28. Presented a paper entitled “**Social concern, Human Rights and good governance**” in the two day **National Seminar** jointly organized by Human Rights Commission, New Delhi and Department of Political Science, University of Mysore, Mysore, on 3rd and 4th October, 2011 at Mysore.
29. Presented a paper in the two day **National seminar** on “**Gender Justice and Emerging Trends Assessment and Challenges Ahead**” held on 14th and 15th October, 2011 organized by Department of Political science, Tumkur University, Tumkur.
30. Chaired a session in the two day **State Level Seminar** conducted by Dr.B.R.Ambedkar Research and extension Centre and Dalith Vidyarthi Okkuta held on 5th December, 2011 and 6th December 2011 on the topic “**Insights and possibilities of daliths developments and inclusive growth**”. Held at EMMRC auditorium, MGM Mysore.
31. Presented a paper in the two day state conference conducted by CSSEIP , university of Mysore, Mysore on 15th December 15th and 16th 2011 on the topic “**Inclusive Growth: issues and prospects**”. The main topic of the seminar was “Regional imbalance, Banking Industry and Inclusive Growth in Karnataka/India: a focus on 12th Five year Plan.

32. Presented a paper in two day State seminar on “**Missing Girls and women: issues and Implications**”. The two day seminar was organized jointly by Karnataka State Commission for Women and CSSEIP, University of Mysore on 23rd and 24th January 2012, and the topic of the paper presented was “Issues and concerns of missing girls and women in Karnataka”.
33. Presented a paper entitled “**Legal Plurality of Social Exclusion Focusing on Indian scenario**” in the two day **National level seminar** on “**Politics in India with special reference to Social Exclusion**” organised by the Department of Studies in Political science, University of Mysore, on 28th and 29th February 2012 .
34. Presented a paper entitled “**legal regime of creation of smaller states in India and its implications**” at two day National Seminar on social exclusion in India: self governance, development politics and autonomy movements, Organized centre for the study of social exclusion and inclusive policy, university of Mysore, Mysore, held on August 22nd and 23rd 2012.
35. Presented a paper entitled “**financial inclusion and unorganized sector workers in India**” in the two day National conference organized by CSSEIP, University of Mysore, Mysore (ICSSR sponsored) on October 9th and 10th 2012. The title of the conference was “financial Inclusion in India: Issues and Challenges”.
36. Presented a paper entitled “**Legal Provision towards protection of Old age Persons: a National and International outlook**”, at the **National Conference** on “**Newer concerns of older persons**” organized by Tumkur University, Tumkur on 30th October 2012.
37. Chaired a session in the three day **National seminar** organized by Dr.B.R. Ambedkar Research and Extension Centre, University of Mysore, Mysore on “**Dalit Development and Inclusive Growth: Issues and Prospects**” on 26th November to 28th November 2012 .
38. Presented a paper at the National Seminar on the topic “**Protection of Human Rights of Women under International Law**”, conducted by centre for Women’s Studies, Pondicherry University, on 14th and 15th December, 2012.
39. Presented a paper entitled “**social exclusion as human rights violation**” at one day state level training workshop on human rights and social exclusion, jointly Organized by National Human Right Commission and centre for the study of social exclusion and inclusive policy, university of Mysore, Mysore, held on December 15th 2012.
40. Presented a paper entitled “**New trends in legal research**” in ten days national workshop on advanced research methodology in social sciences, Organized by centre for the study of social exclusion and inclusive policy, university of Mysore, Mysore, held on January 16th to 26th 2013.
41. Presented a paper in the two day National Conference on the topic “**Inclusive Agricultural Growth in India: issues and Challenges**”, organized by CSSEIP, University of Mysore (ICSSR Sponsored) on 30th and 31st January 2013. The paper presented on the topic was “Special Economic Zones in India: Need for rethinking”.
42. Presented a paper at the UGC sponsored **National seminar** on the topic “**Child sex Tourism and protection of Human rights**” conducted by Gobi Arts and Science College Erode , Tamil Nadu on 7th February 2013.

43. Presented a paper at the UGC sponsored **National Level Seminar**, conducted by Basudev Somani College, Kuvempu Nagar, Mysore on the topic “Human Rights, issues and challenges” on 22nd February, 2013 and the title of the paper is “**Human rights, and the Rights of the marginalized communities**”.
44. Presented a Paper at the one day **National Symposium** on Refugee Protection and UNHCR organized jointly by Department of Studies in law, University of Mysore, Mysore and the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees, Chief of Mission (UNHCR), New Delhi, on 8th March, 2013 and the title of the Paper is “**Refugee protection and Constitutional Perspectives**”.
45. Presented a paper at the two day UGC sponsored **National Seminar** conducted by “the Gandhi Gram Rural Institute-Deemed University Dindigal Tamil Nadu on the topic “Millennium Development Goals: Strategies, Achievements and Challenges” on 8th March, 2013 and the title of the paper is “**Socio-economic and Legal status of women in India: an Overview**”.
46. Presented a paper entitled “**New development in data analysis- exclusion groups**” at two day National workshop on developments in statistical methods for data analysis of excluded groups Organized by centre for the study of social exclusion and inclusive policy, university of Mysore, Mysore, held on March 20th and 21st 2013.
47. Presented a paper at the two day **National Seminar** conducted by Tamil Nadu Dr. Ambedkar Law University, Chennai (In association with Ministry of Environment and Forests, Government of India) on the topic “**Biological Conservation of Land, Water and Forests: Sustainable Practices and Legal Strategies**” on 22nd and 23rd March, 2013, and the title of the paper is “**Eco-tourism and Law**”.
48. Presented a paper in the two day national conference organized by CSSEIP, University of Mysore (ICSSR sponsored) on the topic “**Inclusive Higher Education and Marginalized Sections: dynamics and Discourses**”, on 1st and 2nd August 2013. The title of the paper presented is “Representation of SCs and STs in Higher Education”.
49. Presented a paper at the **National Seminar** on the topic “**Karnataka Dalith Chaluvalli Matthu Sahitya**”, organized by Central University, Karnataka Gulbarga and the title of the paper was “**Karnataka Dalitha Chaluvalliya Mele Ambedkaraar Paatra Matthu Parinama**” on 24th and 25th September 2013.
50. Presented a paper at the two day National conference on the topic “**Inclusive development of marginalized group in contemporary India: issues and Challenges**”. The conference was organized by CSSEIP, University of Mysore, Mysore and the conference topic was. “Human Rights Protection for marginalized groups in India”. Issues and Challenges” on 27th and 28th September, 2013.
51. Presented a paper in the two day national conference organized by CSSEIP, University of Mysore (ICSSR sponsored) on the topic “**Social Exclusion and Reservation policy in India: New Debates**”, on 12th and 13th November, 2013. The topic of the paper presented was “Constitutional Provisions and Reservation policy in India: Dimension and Discourse.
52. Presented a paper at the **National Seminar** on the topic “**Gandhi concept of ideal village and its contemporary relevance**”, organized by University of Mysore

Gandhi Bhavan, Mysore on 29th March 2014. The title of paper was “**Gandhi’s vision of Gram Swaraj- contemporary relevance and challenges**”.

53. Presented a paper at the **state level seminar** on the topic “ **Legal Issues in Food Security**” organized by Karnataka Institute for Law and Parliamentary Reform (KILPAR) and Vidyavardhaka Law college Mysore, on 29th March, 2014.
54. Presented a paper at the **National level** seminar on the topic “Recent Trends in Indian Politics” organized by the Department of Political Science, Bangalore on 30th April 2014. The title of paper was **Elections in India- Law and Realty**.
55. Presented a paper at the two day National Seminar on the topic “**Two Decades of CEDAW: Challenges and Responses- National and International Perspectives**” organized by the Tamil Nadu Dr. Ambedkar Law University, Chennai. On 9th August 2014. The title of the topic was “Trafficking in children-problems and Perspectives”.
56. Presented a paper at the **International Conference** on the topic “**Teacher education Practices and Innovative Trends**” organized by Pondicherry University on 20th August 2014. The title of paper was “**Legal Perspective of Teacher Education**”.
57. Presented a paper in the two day national conference organized by CSSEIP, University of Mysore (ICSSR sponsored) on the topic “**Rural Development and inclusive Growth: New Debates**” on 21st and 22nd August 2014. The topic of the paper presented was “ Issues and challenges in Mahatma Gandhi national rural employment Guarantee Act”.
58. Presented a paper at the **International Seminar** on the topic “**Development and Human rights in the context of Environmental Protection**”. The seminar was organized by the University college of Law and P.G. Department of Studies and Research in law, Bangalore university in association with British Council, Chennai. The Main topic of the seminar was *Indo-UK perspective on public and Transactional Laws*.
59. Presented a paper at the **International Conference** on the topic “**Treatment of Ethnic Tribes in Post-colonial India and Policy Challenges**”. The conference was **organized** by Centre for the Study of Social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy, University of Mysore, Mysore on 18th and 19th December, 2014. The topic of conference is “**Ethnicity, Discrimination and Social Exclusion of Minorities and Margins: Post Colonial Debates**”.
60. Chaired a technical session at the **International Conference** held on the topic “**Ethnicity, Discrimination and Social Exclusion of Minorities and Margins: Post Colonial Debates**”. Organized by Centre for the Study of Social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy, University of Mysore, Mysore on 18th and 19th December, 2014.
61. I was discussant at the **International Conference** held on the topic “**Ethnicity, Discrimination and Social Exclusion of Minorities and Margins: Post Colonial Debates**”. Organized by Centre for the Study of Social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy, University of Mysore, Mysore on 18th and 19th December, 2014.
62. Presented a paper at the two day National **Conference** on the topic “**providing legitimacy to the Intelligence and Investigative Agency**”. The two day National Conference organized by School of Law, Christ University, Bangalore, on 13th and

14th January, 2015 and the topic of the conference was **Constitutional Appointments: Vignettes and Vicissitudes, 2015**.

63. Presented a paper at the two day **International Seminar** on the topic “**Status of Tribals in India**”. The two day international seminar was organized by The Tamil Nadu Dr. Ambedkar Law University Chennai India on 28th to 30th January 2015. The main theme of the seminar was “Agro Bio-diversity and 20 years of WTO”.
64. Presented a paper at the two day **International seminar on the topic “Micro finance and economic empowerment of women”**. The two day international seminar was organized by Mysore University Third Sector Research Resource Centre and SBRR Mahajana first Grade College Mysore, on 2nd and 3rd February, 2015. The topic of the seminar was “Self help initiatives, Microfinance and Sustainable Development”.
65. Presented a paper at the **one day National seminar** on the topic “**Police Reform and Human Rights**”. One day national conference was organized by Department of Studies and Research in law, Karnataka State Open University, Mysore on 3rd February, 2015. The topic of the seminar was “**Human Rights- a Natural and Positive Edict**”.
66. **Presented a paper at the two day National Seminar on the topic” Prevention of Superstitious Practices-Need of the Hour”**. This two day National seminar was organized by BMS college of Law, Bangalore on 13th and 14th February 2015. The broad theme of the seminar was Law in Action- a vision for 2020.
67. **Presented a paper at the two day National Seminar on the topic “surrogacy-boon or bane”**. This two day National seminar was organized by BMS college of Law, Bangalore on 13th and 14th February 2015. The broad theme of the seminar was Law in Action- a vision for 2020.
68. Presented a paper at the two days **International Seminar** on the topic “**health problems of old age communities in India- A critical appraisal**”. The two day seminar was organized on “**community empowerment in changing world-issues and challenges**”. This seminar was jointly organized by University of Mysore, Karnataka State Planning Board, Karnataka State Open University, Development Research Foundation, Mysore and Naresuan University, Thailand, on 27th and 28th February 2015 at MGM, Mysore.
69. Presented a paper at the **One day state level seminar** on the topic “**Pourakarmika community**” jointly organized by Dr. B.R. Ambedkar and Babu Jagjivan Ram Study and extension Centre on 28th February, 2015 at Mysore.
70. Presented a paper in the two day **International Seminar** on “**Inclusive Education- perspectives and challenges**” held on 6th and 7th March 2015 organized by DOS and Research in education, Karnataka State Open University, Mukta Gangothri, Mysore.
71. Presented a paper in the two day **national Seminar** on “**social exclusion of dalit women in 21st century: strategies for inclusion**” title of the paper was “constitutional safeguard of dalit women in India” held on 12th and 13th March 2015 organized by CSSEIP, the Gandhigram rural institute (deemed university) Gandhigram, Dindigal District Tamilnadu

72. Presented a paper in two day in Intentional student conference on “ **Indo-Iranian scientific relation and co-operation: opportunity and challenges**” on 5th and 6th march 2015.university of Mysore, Mysore.
73. Presented a paper in two day National Seminar on the topic “**Health Status of elderly women living in old age homes in Karnataka: an Overview**” on 9th and 10th October 2015. The seminar was organized by St. Philomena’s College, Mysore and the title of the seminar was “Women’s Mental Health”.
74. Presented a paper in two day National Seminar on the topic “**Language policy in India: a Constitutional Perspectives**” on 16th and 17th October, 2015. The Seminar was conducted jointly by JSS Law College, Mysore, and Central Institute of Indian Language, Mysore and the seminar topic was “Law and Language”.
75. Participated as a panellist in the two day National Seminar on the topic “**Language Policy in India: a constitutional Perspectives**” on 16th and 17th October, 2015. The Seminar was conducted jointly by JSS Law College, Mysore, and Central Institute of Indian Language, Mysore and the seminar topic was “Law and Language”.
76. Presented a paper on the topic “**Human rights of the vulnerable sections of the society**” in the one day training programme on Human rights organized jointly by Vidhya Vardhaka Law college, Mysore and National Human rights commission, New Delhi, On 31st October, 2015.
77. Presented a paper on the topic “Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace: an overview” in the four day **International Conference** on “Medical and Social Sciences” jointly organized by Department of Community Medicine and University of Mysore, Mysore. The conference was held 24th to 27th November, 2015 and the theme of conference was “Gender Equity: Social Issues and Health Challenges in today’s Context”.
78. Presented a paper on the topic “Human Trafficking and Human Resource Development- a critical analysis” in the **International Conference** on “Managing Human Resources at the Workplace”. The conference was organized by SDM Institute for Management Development on December 4th and 5th 2015.
79. Presented a paper on the topic “*some reformative suggestions for improving present democratic governance in India*” in the National level Seminar on “Democratic Governance in India: Problems and Prospects”. The seminar was organized by Department of Studies in Political Science, University of Mysore, Mysore, on 10th December, 2015.ABEDA INAMDAR SENIOR COLLEGE of Arts Science & commerce, Pune, Maharashtra on 16th and 17th December, 2015.
80. Presented a paper on the topic “**the Maternity Benefit Act, 1961: an Overview**” in the two day **National Seminar** on the topic Maternity Benefit Scheme: Status, Contours and Strategies. The seminar was organized by Institute by Institute for Development Research and Alternatives: Tirupati and Department of Adult and Continuing Education, S.V. University: Tirupati on 18th and 19th December, 2015.
81. Presented a paper on the topic “*problems of senior citizen*” in the **two day National** seminar on “Human Rights Education: Prospective and Prospects” held

on 28th and 29th 2016. The National seminar was organized by Department of History, Archaeology and Culture, Dravidian University, Andhra Pradesh.

82. Presented a paper on the topic “ ***Evolution of Human rights***” in the two National seminar on “ Changing Dimensions of Human rights” held on 23rd and 24th January 2016. The National Seminar was organized by Karnataka University Dharwad (Sir Siddappa Kambli Law College, Dharawad).
83. Presented a paper on the topic “ **Aadhar and the legal challenges**” in the two day **national seminar** on “ social security and social Inclusion: opportunities and Challenges” held on 25th and 26th February, 2016. The National Seminar was organized by Centre for the Study of social exclusion and Inclusive Policy, University of Mysore, Mysore.
84. Chaired a technical session in the two day national conference on “***Social security and Social Inclusion: Opportunities and challenges***”. The seminar was organized by CSSEIP, university of Mysore, Mysore on 25th and 26th February, 2016.
85. Presented a paper in the two day National conference on the topic “ social security protection for unorganized workers in India; myth and reality on 25th February 2016. The conference was organized by CSSEIP sponsored by ICSSR New Delhi. The thrust area of conference was “Social Security and social Inclusion: opportunities and challenge.
86. Participated and acted as observer in the “ **Model United Nations conference**” held on February, 2016. The conference was conducted by department of Studies in law, University of Mysore, Mysore.
87. Presented a paper on the topic “ ***Trafficking in women***” in the one day National level seminar on Human rights jointly organized by Department of Studies in Law and Karnataka Institute for Law and Parliamentary Reforms (KILPAR). The seminar was held on 26th February, 2016.
88. Chaired a technical session in the one day National level seminar on Human rights jointly organized by Department of Studies in Law and Karnataka Institute for Law and Parliamentary Reforms (KILPAR). The seminar was held on 26th February, 2016.
89. Presented a paper on the topic “ Development and Human rights” in the two day National level seminar on “Human rights of vulnerable sections of the society” organized by Department of Studies in Law . The seminar was held on 8th and 9th March 2016.
90. Chaired a technical session in the two day **National Seminar** on “Human rights of vulnerable sections of the society”. The seminar was organized by department of Studies in law, University of Mysore on 8th and 9th March, 2016.
91. Presented a paper in the two day **International Conference** on the topic “ Refugees in international law and their right to compensation”. The international seminar was organized by Department of Studies in Law, University of Mysore,

Mysore on 28th and 29th March, 2016 and thrust area of seminar was “New Dimensions in Public International Law.

92. Chaired a technical session in the two day ***International conference*** organized by Department of Studies in Law, University of Mysore, Mysore on 28th and 29th March, 2016 and thrust area of seminar was “New Dimensions in Public International Law.
93. Presented a paper in two day ***international Seminar*** on the topic “***Domestic violence- violation of Human rights of women***”. The International seminar was organized by Department of political science and Public administration wing of Annamalai University on 29th and 30th March, 2016. The thrust area of the seminar was “Human rights in India- current issues and challenges”.
94. Presented a paper in one day ***National Seminar*** on the topic “***Socio and legal status of women street vendors in Mysore city***”. The seminar was organized by Government Law College, Hassan in association with KILPAR on 13th April, 2016 and the thrust area of seminar was “Protection of Marginalized women in India”.
95. Presented a paper in two day ***national seminar*** on the topic “critical analysis of LCC and ICC under the Act” the seminar was organized by BILS Bangalore on 20th and 21st April 2016 and the thrust area of seminar was “Combating workplace sexual Harassment of women”.
96. Presented a paper in two day national Conference on the topic “***the role of Telecom regulatory Authority of India in Promoting Net Neutrality***”. The conference was organized by J.S.S. Law College, Mysore on 26th and 27th April 2016 and the main thrust area of conference was “Indian Legal system- Emerging Dimensions”.
97. Presented a paper in the one day National Seminar on the topic “Human rights Protection of women under medical termination of Pregnancy Act”. The seminar was jointly organized by S.B.B.R Mahajana Law College Mysore, and KILPAR on 29th April, 2016 and the thrust area of seminar was “Domestic violence and Human Rights” .
98. Presented a paper in the one day National Seminar on the topic “a Human rights approach of access to information: a critical study” . The seminar was jointly organized by Vidhyavardhaka Law College Mysore, and KILPAR on 30th April, 2016 and the thrust area of seminar was “Right to Information Act, 2015.
99. Secured best paper award in the National conference held in the J.S.S. Law college, Mysore for the presentation of topic “the role of telecom regulatory authority of India in promoting New neutrality. The conference was held on 26th and 27th April, 2016 and thrust area of conference was “ Indian Legal System-emerging dimensions”.
100. Presented a paper in one day National seminar on the topic “ ***constitutional validity of reservation in higher education***” . The seminar was organized by Government first Grade College for women, Holenarsipura on 4th May 2016. The

thrust area of seminar was “Higher Education in India- New Paradigms and challenges.

101. Presented a paper in the National seminar on the topic “*farmer’s rights, causes for suicide and strategies for the prevention of suicide*”. The seminar was jointly organized by Department of Economics, sir. M. Visweswaraya P.G.Centre, Mandya and Department of economics, government women’s college, Mandya on 15th and 16th April, 2016. The thrust area of seminar was “Farmers suicide in India: Causes and Cure”.
102. Chaired a technical session in the National conference on the topic “ Computer literacy and Research”. The conference was organized by J.S.S. Law college, Mysore on 26th and 27th April, 2016 and the thrust area of the conference was “Indian Legal System- emerging Dimensions.
103. Chaired a technical session in the National conference on the topic “ Protection of women under family Law”. The conference was organized by J.S.S. Law college, Mysore on 26th and 27th April, 2016 and the thrust area of the Conference was “Indian Legal System- emerging Dimensions.
104. Presented a paper at the one day National level seminar on the topic “right to information as a tool for openness and accountability in Indian Governance: an overview”. The seminar was organized jointly by KILPAR, Bangalore and VVLC Mysore on 30th April, 2016 and thrust are of the seminar was “ Right to Information Act,2005: an experience of a decade”.
105. Chaired a technical session at the one day National level seminar on the topic “right of information Act, 2005”. The seminar was organized jointly by the KILPAR Bangalore and VVLC Mysore on 30th April, 2016.
106. Presented a paper in the International Conference on the topic “Surrogacy in India: Legal, Ethical and Human Rights implications”. The conference was jointly organized by University of Mysore, Mysore, Karnataka State Planning Board, Development Research Foundation, Mysore, ISBR, Bangalore and CREST Bangalore on 25th and 26th June 2016. The thrust area of the conference was “Advances in collaborative Research for Economics, Management, Humanities, social Sciences and Computer Technology.
107. Chaired a technical session in the International Conference. The conference was jointly organized by University of Mysore, Mysore, Karnataka State Planning Board, Development Research Foundation, Mysore, ISBR, Bangalore and CREST Bangalore on 25th and 26th June 2016. The thrust area of the conference was “Advances in collaborative Research for Economics, Management, Humanities, social Sciences and Computer Technology.
108. Presented a paper on the topic “**Tribal Women and Skill Development**” in the National Seminar conducted by the Centre for the study of social exclusion and Inclusive policy, University of Mysore, Mysore. The seminar was held on July 1st and 2nd 2016 and thrust area of seminar was “ Empowering Women through skill Development challenges and opportunities”.

109. Chaired a technical session in the national seminar conducted by the Centre for the study of social exclusion and inclusive Policy, University of Mysore, Mysore on the topic “Empowering Women through skill Development challenges and opportunities”. the seminar was held on 1st and 2nd July 2016.
110. Presented a paper on the topic “ ***Agriculture in the Vedic age***” in the one day National seminar conducted by the DOS in Sanskrit department on 19th July 2016. The thrust area of the conference was “Agriculture in Sanskrit literature”.
111. Presented a paper on the topic “ ***Privacy rights of third genders in India***” in the one day state level training Programme conducted by M. Krishna Law college Hassan and National Human Rights Commission New Delhi on 6th October, 2016. The main theme of training was “rights of transgenders in a contemporary society”.
112. Presented a paper on the topic “ ***Legal History of Indian Tribes***” in the two National workshop conducted by the Centre for the study of social exclusion and Inclusive Policy, University of Mysore, Mysore, on 20th and 21st October, 2016. The main theme of workshop is “*transition of particularly vulnerable Tribal groups (Primitive) in India; an ethno-historical relook*”.
113. Presented a paper on the topic “ ***freedom to Trade as a Human Right***” in the two day National seminar conducted jointly by National Human Rights Commission and Department of studies in law, University of Mysore, Mysore on 21st and 22nd October, 2016. The main theme of seminar was “ Sensitizing Human rights- a Third World Countries Approach”.
114. Chaired a session in the two day National seminar conducted jointly by National Human Rights Commission and Department of studies in law, University of Mysore, Mysore on 21st and 22nd October, 2016. The main theme of seminar was “Sensitizing Human rights- a Third World Countries Approach”.
115. Presented a paper in the one day National conference conducted by the SDM Law college Mangalore on 25th November, 2016, on the topic “ ***unsustainable Bangalore steel flyover***” . The main theme of the conference was “ development and environment challenges: issues and strategies for sustainable development.
116. Presented a paper in the two day International conference conducted by the SDM Institute for Management Development on 9th and 10th December, 2016, on the topic “ ***reason for change of job***”. The main theme of the conference was “5th International Conference on Managing Human Resources at the workplace”.
117. Presented a paper in the two day national seminar on the topic “ ***mental health condition of women prisoners***” on 9th and 10th December, 2016. The seminar was organized by Christ University Bangalore and theme of the seminar was” Empowering Lives: Mental Health and Well being in an inclusive world”.
118. Presented a paper in the two day National conference on the topic “ ***Effects of demonetization on street vendors***” on 18th and 19th January, 2017. The seminar was

conducted by the Centre for the Study of exclusion and Inclusive Policy, University of Mysore, Mysore and theme of the seminar was “Dynamics of Poverty, inequality and Exclusion in Urban India: Debates and Discussions”.

119. Chaired a technical session in the two day National conference on the topic “***Dynamics of Poverty, inequality and Exclusion in Urban India: Debates and Discussions***” on 18th and 19th January 2017. The conference was conducted by the Centre for the study of social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy, University of Mysore, Mysore, Mysore.
120. Presented a paper on the topic “***right to health as fundamental right***” in the XL Indian Social Science Congress conducted by the University of Mysore, Mysore from 19th December, 2016 to 23rd December 2016. The social science congress was jointly organized by Indian Academy of Social Sciences and University of Mysore, Mysore.
121. Chaired a technical session in the XL Indian Social Science Congress held on 19th December, 2016 to 23rd December, 2016. . The Social Science congress was jointly organized by Indian Academy of Social Sciences and University of Mysore, Mysore.
122. Presented a paper on the topic “***challenges faced by women street vendors in business development***” at the two day National Conference conducted by the Department of Studies in law on 17th and 18th February, 2017. The thrust area of conference was “Human rights, Duties and Education with special reference to women.
123. Chaired a technical session in the two day National conference conducted by Department of studies in law on 17th and 18th February 2017. The thrust area of conference was “***Human Rights, Duties and Education with special reference to women.***”
124. Presented a paper on the topic Judicial Reforms and Judicial activism on women rights in two day National seminar held on 10th and 11th March, 2017. The seminar was conducted by Department of Political Science, Vijaya Nagara Sri Krishnadeva raya University Bellary. The thrust area of seminar was on “***Recent Developments and Trends in India’s Democracy***”.
125. Presented a paper at the state level seminar conducted by the Government Law College, Kolar on the topic “***Human Rights and Media***” on 11th March, 2017. I was the chairperson to this one day seminar.
126. Presented a paper at the one day training programme conducted by JSS law college, Mysore on the topic “***the rights of vulnerable groups***” on 4th March, 2017
127. Presented a paper at the two day National seminar conducted by the JSS law college, Mysore, on the topic “writing of research thesis” on 7th and 8th April 2017. The thrust area of conference was “***Research in law-approaches and Techniques***”.

128. Chaired a technical session at the two day National seminar conducted by the JSS law college, Mysore, on 7th and 8th April 2017, on the topic. Research in law-approaches and Techniques”.
129. Presented a paper at the one day National seminar conducted by the Bangalore University on the topic “ *Foreign Direct Investment in Retail vis-à-vis the rights of street vendors*, on 29th May 2017. The thrust area of conference was “ensuring social justice in the era of globalization: issues and challenges.
130. Presented a paper at the one day International Multidisciplinary Conference on the topic “Extradition is not a rule, will of the state” on 12th August, 2017. The conference was jointly organized by the Common wealth society for Innovation and Research and BMS College of Law, Bengaluru.
131. Presented a paper at the one day national conference on the topic” protection of women under Indian Constitution” held on 24th November, 2017. The conference was organized by the Department of Studies and research in sociology, Tumkur University, Tumkur.
132. Presented a paper at the two day National Conference on the topic “ Utility of ICT in the field of Rural Health” held on 10th and 11th January 2018. The conference was organized by the Centre for the Study of Social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy, University of Mysore Mysore the thrust area of conference was Emerging Rural Health Issues in India”.
133. Chaired a technical session at the two day National conference conducted by the Centre for the Study of Social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy, University of Mysore, Mysore. The conference was held on 10th and 11th January 2018.
134. Presented a paper as a resource person in the two day workshop conducted by the Dr.B.R. Ambedkar, Research and Extension Centre, University of Mysore, Mysore and drafted the syllabus for M.A in Ambedkar Studies and with special reference to “ Dr. Ambedkar and Law” on January, 17th and 18th 2018.
135. Presented a paper at the one day national conference on the topic “significance of corporate governance” on 31st January, 2018. The main theme of conference was “corporate streamlining” and conference was organized by JSS Law college, Mysore.
136. Presented a paper as a resource person in the Six days Regional Level Research Methodology workshop for SC/ST research scholars in Social sciences on 2nd February, 2018 on the topic “Ethics in Research and how to avoid Plagiarism”. The workshop was organized by Centre for the Study of social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy, University of Mysore, Mysore.
137. Presented a paper as a resource person at two National seminar on the topic “ Health concerns of street vendors: a case study of Mysore city” on 16th and 17th February, 2018. The conference was jointly organized by UGC-UPE-II, and Department of studies in social work and main theme of the conference was “ Issues of social Development- A social work response.”

138. Presented a paper as a resource person at one day National Policy conference on the topic "indecent representation of women and pseudo photograph on social media" on 19th February, 2018. The seminar was conducted jointly by the University of Potential Excellence (UPE-II) and Centre for the Study of Social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy, university of Mysore, Mysore. And the main theme of conference was "social Media for digital and Social Inclusion: cultural, technological and Economic implication".
139. Chaired a session at one day National Policy Conference on the topic "social Media for digital and Social Inclusion: cultural, technological and Economic implication" conducted jointly by University of Potential Excellence (UPE-II), university of Mysore, Mysore and Centre for the Study of social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy. And the conference was held on 19th February, 2018.
140. Chaired a session in one day national seminar conducted by National Human Rights Commission and University of Mysore on 9th March 2018. The main theme of the seminar was 'poverty, social justice and Human rights'.
141. Presented a paper as a resource person in a two day National Seminar on the topic "a critique on impact of some legislations on Panchayat raj system in India", held on 8th a 9th March, 2018. The seminar was conducted by Department of studies in Public Administration, university of Mysore, Mysore, and the main theme of "Decentralization and Empowerment for Rural Development: the Role of Panchayat Raj Institutions in India".
142. Presented a paper at two day National seminar on the topic "Food security and Social Inclusion in India". The seminar was conducted by the Centre for the Study of Social Exclusion and Inclusive policy, university of Mysore, Mysore, on 14th and 15th March 2018, main theme of seminar was "food security and social Inclusion in India".
143. Chaired a technical session in the two day National symposium on the emergence of the Philosophy of International Law- a bird's eye view on Jurisprudence". The symposium was conducted by the Department of studies in law, University of Mysore, Mysore, on 27th and 28th March, 2018.
144. Presented a paper at a two day International Conference on the topic "*Socio-legal status of women street vendors: a study*". The conference was conducted by Government first grade College and P.G. Centre in association with University College of Education Bangalore University, Chickballapur" on 27th and 28th March 2018. The main theme of the conference was "multidisciplinary researches in empowerment of women water resource management, culture, tourism and recent emerging trends in India".
145. Presented a paper at one day National Seminar on the topic "women's right to say no". The conference was conducted by Vidyavardhaka Law College, Mysore on 5th May, 2018 and the main theme of the conference was "empowerment of women in India- issues and challenges".

146. Chaired a first technical session at one day National seminar conducted by Vidyavardhaka Law College, Mysore on 5th May, 2018 and the main theme of the conference was “empowerment of women in India- issues and challenges”.
147. Chaired a technical session in the two day national conference on 13th and 14th August 2018 organized jointly by Basudeva Somani College, and Centre for the study of social exclusion and Inclusive Policy. The main theme of the seminar was “Tribal Development and corporate social Responsibility: Issues and prospective”
148. Chaired a technical session in the two day national seminar conducted by the Centre for the study of social exclusion and inclusive Policy” on 29th and 30th August 2019. The main theme of the seminar was “make in India and digital India: empowering and transformation for inclusive growth”.
149. Presented a paper on “cyber offences and digitalising the banking sector” in the two nation seminar conducted by the “Centre for the study of Social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy” on 29th and 30th August 2018. The main theme of seminar was “Make in India and Digital India: empowering and transformation for inclusive growth”.
150. Presented a paper on “Ethics in Research” in the two day workshop conducted on 10th and 11th January 2019 by UGC-CSSEIP and Karnataka State Council for science and Technology. The main theme of the workshop was” technical writing and publications, grant proposals, funding agencies and soft skills in scientific research”.
151. Presented a paper on “contract farming” in the two day National seminar held on 7th and 8th February, 2019 conducted by CSSEIP, university of Mysore, Mysore. The main theme of seminar was” agrarian and farmers suicide in India: causes, consequences and remedies”.
152. Chaired a technical session at the two day National seminar held on 7th and 8th February, 2019, conducted by CSSEIP, University of Mysore, Mysore, the main theme of seminar was” agrarian and farmers suicide in India: causes, consequences and remedies”.
153. Presented a paper on the topic “ honour killing- a gross violation of human rights” at one National conference on “New Horizons in International Human Rights law- critical discourses organized by Department of Studies in law, University of mysore. The conference was held on 21st March 2019.
154. Presented a paper on the topic “international Law and Organizations with reference to International boarder” on 25th March 2019. The seminar was organized by Maharaja College Mysore and the main theme of seminar was” Indian Foreign policy: continuity and change in 21st century”.
155. Presented a paper in one day National Seminar on the topic “ role of judiciary in protecting the Human rights in extradition” on 25th March 2019. The seminar was conducted by Vidyavardhaka Law College and main theme of seminar was “ the role of judiciary in protecting Human rights in India: issues and challenges.

156. Chaired a technical session at the one day National seminar held on 25th May, 2019, conducted by Vidyavardhaka Law College, Mysore. The main theme of conference was “Role of Judiciary in protecting Human Rights in India; Issues and challenges”.
157. Presented a paper in one day national seminar on the topic “a question of fair elections-EVMs and RTI” on 13th June 2019 at Vaikunta Baliga College of Law Udupi. The main theme of seminar was “reflections on free speech and expression in the backdrop of social media in India”
158. Presented a course material in two day National work shop on the topic “Constitutional and International perspective of health” on 18th and 19th June 2019. The workshop was jointly conducted by Centre for the Study of Social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy, University of Mysore Mysore and National Academy for Medical Science(NAMS) and the main theme of the workshop was “ accelerating Universal Health Coverage in India: Issues and Challenges”.
159. Presented a paper in two day National work on the topic “The Global intent and Tribal distinctiveness in North East India” on 1st and 2nd August, 2019. The workshop was jointly conducted by Centre for the Study of Social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy, University of Mysore, Mysore and Basudeva Somani college, Mysore, and the main theme of the seminar was “Ignored claims” status of Nomadic and semi Nomadic Tribal groups in India.
160. Chaired technical session in two day National seminar conducted jointly by Centre for the Study of Social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy, University of Mysore, Mysore and Basudeva Somani college, Mysore, on 2nd August, 2019 and the main theme of the seminar was “Ignored claims” status of Nomadic and semi Nomadic Tribal groups in India.
161. Presented a paper in the two day National Seminar on the topic “ the concerns of women entrepreneurship” on 9th and 10th January 2020. The seminar was conducted by centre for the study of social exclusion and inclusive policy, university of Mysore, Mysore and thrust area of the seminar was “ Women entrepreneurship and skill development issues, challenges and opportunities”.
162. Chaired a session in the two day National seminar conducted by the “centre for the Study of social exclusion and inclusive policy on 9th January 2020. The thrust area of seminar was “Women entrepreneurship and Skill Development Issues, Challenges and Opportunities.
163. Presented a paper on the topic “ Ambedkar’s Philosophy on Indian Constitution” in the two day National workshop on “Dr.b.R.Ambedkar’s thoughts on Socio-Economic Development of India: A Revisit”. The conference was organized by Dr.B.R.ambedkar Studies and Research Centre, KSOU, Mysore on 20-21st January 2020.
164. Presented a paper on the topic “ **an introduction to Human rights**” in the one day basic training workshop on “Basic Training workshop on Human Rights”. The training programme was organized by the Centre for the study of social exclusion and inclusive policy on 31st January 31st 2020.

165. Presented a paper on the topic “ scientific research methodology and its relevance” in the three day National workshop on “Legal Research Methodology” organized by Department of studies and Research in law, University of Mysore, Mysore on 6th to 8th February, 2020.
166. Presented a paper on the “ impact of cyber crimes on International Peace and security” in the one day International Model United Nations conference organized by the School of law, University of Mysore, Mysore on 2nd March, 2020.
167. Presented a paper on the topic “ basic structure of Indian Constitution” in the two day National workshop organized by Department of Political Science, Karnataka University Dharwad, on 7th March 2020. The main theme of the seminar was “ Indian Constitutional Philosophy: theory and Practice”

<u>List of Research Articles Published</u>				
Sl. No	Title of the Article	Name of the Journal	Status of the Journal	Date of Publication
1	Right to Information/ Open government: Boon or Bane	Indian Law Reports (Karnataka series)	State	15 th December 1998
2	Should we go back to Mandal Panchayat?	Indian Express	National	13 th January 1999
3	Mandal Panchayat: the challenges before us.	Parliamentary Affairs	State	Febraury-1999
4	Teaching Environment Laws.	University News	National	19 th July 1999
5	Corruption & its nature: A critical analyses.	Criminal Law Journal	National	November-1999
6	Judicial interpretation of Art 12 of Indian Constitution.	Supreme Court Journal.	National	November-2000
7	Compulsory Primary Education: A distant dream to be achieved.	Cochin Law Review.	University	September- December 2000
8	Right to housing: A mandate for 21 st century.	Indian Bar Review	National	2002(3&4)
9	Legal nature of International Criminal court.	Indian Bar Review.	National	2003(1)
10	Critical analysis of “Sishir Ranjan Saha v. The state of Tripura & others”: A case for reconsideration.	All India Reporters.	National	2003
11	Privatisation of public under takings and its impact in India.	Cochin Law Review.	University	March & June 2000.
12	Right to food: Need for changes in the policy.	Indian Socio- Legal Journal.	International	March & June 2002.
13	Patent Illiteracy: A threat to economic growth	University News	National	July 2004.
14	Right to drinking Water: Need for changes in the policy	Indian Bar Review	National	October-December 2003

15	Hindu Religious Institutions- Appointment of priests: Some Ancillary Issues.	Indian Socio-Legal Journal.	International	2005-Volume XXXI
16	Political Empowerment of Women In India: A Critique.	Women- Child Law & Society.	College	Vidhya Vardhaka Law College, Mysore, 2006.
17	Cruelty as Compoundable Offence: A Critique	Criminal Law Journal	National	2006 Criminal Law Journal August 2006.
18	Registration of Design: Need a Fresh look	Indian Bar Review	National	Vol.XXXII (1&2) 2005
19	Judges Inquiry Bill 2006- an appraisal	Mysore University Law Journal	University	Vol.1, March 2008
20	International Law and Transfer Pricing analysis of legal aspects(Co- authored with G.Raghu)	Mysore University Law Journal	University	Vol.1, March 2008
21	Feminist Perspectives of Compulsory registration of Marriages (Co-author with R. Usharani)	Mysore University Law Journal	University	Vol.1, March 2008
22	Political empowerment of women In India: an analysis	Indian Socio Legal Journal	National	Vol XXXIV 2008
23	Creating Legal space for Refugees in India	Karnataka Law Journal	State	2009 (2) K.L.J.
24	The Constitutional Perspective of Social Justice	Supreme Court Journal	National	2009 (2) S. C. J
25	The Constitutional Dimensions of Refugees: A Critical Study	Karnataka Law Journal	State	2009 (3) K.L.J
26	Refugee Crisis in Indian Perspectives: Need for Reforms	Karnataka Law Journal	State	2009 (3) K.L.J

27	Emancipation of Untouchability: Constitutional perspective	Supreme Court Journal	National	2009(4) S.C.J
28	Tibetan Refugees in India: A Critical Study	Karnataka Law Journal	State	2009 (4) K.L.J
29	Pornography and Obscenity on the Web: Need a Strict Law	Supreme Court Journal	National	2009 (5) SCJ
30	Cyber Crimes: Need Effective Law	Criminal Law Journal	National	August 2009 Vol. 115 Part. 1316
31	Role of ICRC in Protecting Sick and Wounded During War Crisis	Karnataka Law Journal	State	2009 (5) K.L.J
32	Historical Development of the Press Law: in Indian Perspective	Karnataka Law Journal	State	2009 (5) K.L.J
33	Rights of the child and child labour in India: A Critical Study	Legal News and Views	National	2009 October Vol. 23 No 10
34	A Critical study of the constitutional provisions in the light of the report of the state high power committee for regional imbalance in Karnataka	Legal Opus	State	October 2009 Issue No.4
35	Social Security for the Aged: Need a Human Look	Indian Bar Review	National	Vol. XXXV (1to4)2008 Published in 2009
36	Legal Response to Female Foeticide in India	Legal News and Views	National	2009 December Vol. 23 No 12
37	The Amendment to the Child Labour (Prohibition and Regulation) Act, 1986	Legal News and Views	National	2010 February Vol 24 No 2

38	Laws Relating to Protection of Children	Karnataka Law Journal	State	2010 (1) January
39	Causes for The Refugee Flows: A Critical Study	Supreme Court Journal	National	2010 (2) SCJ
40	The Role of International Committee of Red Cross (ICRC) in Implementing and Enforcing the Humanitarian Law and Human Rights Law in Non-International Armed Conflicts	Karnataka Law Journal	State	2010(2) April
41	Right to Education and Human Rights	Karnataka Law Journal	State	2010(2) April
42	Environmental laws and Human Rights	Supreme Court Journal	National	2010(3) SCJ
43	The Status of International law under the Constitution of India	Karnataka Law Journal	State	2010(3) May
44	Protection of Geographical Indication in India: Some Variations Between TRIPS and Indian Law	Supreme Court Journal	National	2010(4) SCJ
45	Evolution of International Human rights law....	The Karnataka Law Journal	State	2011(3) Kar. L.J
46	Theoretical analysis of domestic application of International Human rights Law within Municipal sphere	The Bangalore Law Journal	State	Vol.4-No.1 June2011
47	Constitutional requirements for conclusions of International Treaties in India	Supreme Laws Today	National	IX (2011) SLJ

48	De-notified Tribes- Historical perspective Reasons for their present pitiable plight and plans to Ameliorate their lot	The Karnataka Law Journal, Bangalore	State	2011(4) Kar. L. J
49	Women Empowerment only through changes in societal mindset	The Karnataka Law Journal, Bangalore	State	2011(4) Kar. L. J
50	Elementary Education in Rural Karnataka- An Analysis	Artha-Journal of social sciences. Bangalore	State(Christ University)	Artha JSS ci Vol.9,NO.2, July- December 2010
51	Problem of corruption- A need for rethinking of existing anti-corruption Laws.	Karnataka Law Journal	State	Vol 2011 (5)
52	Problem of corruption: Human Rights Perspectives.	Indian Law Review: published by the National Law Institute University, Bhopal	National	Volume III 2011
53	Prevention of Corruption: International Law Perspective	Rajiv Gandhi National University of Law Review	National	Vol.1, Number II July-December 2011
54	Child sex Tourism and protection of Human rights	Gobi Arts and science College Erode, Tamil Nadu	College	February 2013 ISBN No. 978-81- 910200-3-8
55	Environmental pollution by Tourism and Protection in India	Asian Journal of development matters	International	Vol.6. 2 nd Dec 2012 No.2 ISSN Print- 0973-9629, ISSN on Line 0976-4674
56	Impact of Corruption on Rural India and Role of E- Governance in prevention of corruption	Asian Journal of development matters	International	Vol .5 (3): Dec 2011, 326-332
57	The eleven highest qualification sources of information in International commercial arbitration (ICA)	Indian streams research Journal(An International Recognition Research Journal)	International	Vol.3, issue 5, June 2013 ISSN: 2230- 7850

58	Street vendors in urban informal sector: financially excluded or included?	A Journal in honour of the common Man	University	2013 ISBN-978-81d-927428-0-9
59	A critique on the problems and perspectives of aged people	International Journal of Social and Economic research	International	Vol. 3, Issue 1 January- March 2013 ISSN:2249-6270
60	Social, Economic and Legal Status of Women in India: an overview	Millennium Development Goals	National	ISBN No. 978-93-313-2438-2
61	International Treaty Law vs. Indian International Taxation Law and General Anti-Avoidance Rules in India (GAAR)- A study.	International Journal of Social and Economic Research	International	Online ISSN:2249-6270, vol.4, Issue 2, April-June 2014
62	Situation analysis of children in Mysore city- India- some Preliminary annotations	Redesigning Inclusive Development	National	Published by Discovery House Pvt. Ltd. 2014 ISBN No. 93-5056-450-5
63	Impact of corruption on Rural India and role of E-governance in prevention of corruption.	Redesigning Inclusive Development	National	Published by Discovery House Pvt. Ltd. 2014 ISBN No. 93-5056-450-5
64	Health problems of old age communities in India: a critical appraisal	Community empowerment in changing world: issues and challenges	International	Published by Book Rix GmbH & Co. Germany. February 2015, ISBN No. 978-3-7368-2021-0
65	Role of Food security Act for Rural Development in India	Sustainable rural Development	University	Professional Book Publisher, Hyderabad. ISBN No. 978-81-909728-8-8 2015
66	Economic Reforms: Income Tax without Borders	Journal of Media and social Development	University of Mysore	October-December 2014, vol. 2 issue 4
67	Constitutional Mandate to curb superstitious practices	Indian Bar Review	National	Vol. XLII (1) 2015
68	Efficient competition for social and economic welfare	Indian Journal.com	International	2014, vol. 4, Issue:4 Online ISSN:22

69	Human Trafficking and Human Resource Development-A Critical analysis	4 th International Conference on Managing Human Resources at the Workplace	International	December 4 th and 5 th , 2015, Mysore, India. ISBN 978-93-83302-07-9
70	Combating trafficking of women: a legal Perspective	AJRA	National	AJRA vol. I Issue II ISSN 2455-5967
70	Social security and social inclusion for unorganized section workers in India- a critique	Social security and social inclusion (edited book)	National	2016 ISBN NO-978-81-910230-3-9
71	Social security for unorganized workers in India- myth and reality	-Do-	National	- Do-
72	Social security and Social Inclusion for unorganized sector workers in India- a critique	Social security and Social Inclusion : Dynamics and Discourses	National	2016 ISBN NO. 978-81-91-230-3-9
73	Social security protection for unorganized workers in India: myth and reality	-Do-	Do	- Do-
74	Adhar and the legal challenges	Social Development in India: Emerging Debates	Do	2016-06-27 ISBN 978-81-931384-7-2
75	Defining and redefining the term food as Constitutional obligation of State	Indian Journal.com	International	ISSN 2249-6270 Doi: 10.5958/2249-6270.2016.00013.1
76	Surrogacy in India: legal, ethical and human rights Implications	Advances in collaborative Research	International	ISBN-978-1534689640
77	Tribal women and skill development	Rethinking skill development and women empowerment	National	ISBN 978-81-927970-5-2
78	Agriculture in the Vedic age	DOS in Sanksrit UOM, Mysore	National	ISBN 978-81-910230 2016

79	The critical analysis in rule of interpolation of Exemption clauses in the standard form of contract.	International journal of Research in Social Sciences	International	ISSN:2249-2496 impact factor (IJRSS)5.650 for 2014 and 6.278 for 2015
80	Reason for change of job	5 th International Conference on Managing Human Resources at the Workplace	International	December 09 th and 10 th 2016 ISBN NO.978-93-83302-19-2
81	Critical analysis of laws relating to women prisoners	International journal of Social and Economic research	International	Vol.6(3)2016 July (July-Sept) Doi: 10.5958/2249-6270.2016.00044.1
82	Violation of Human Rights of Women Prisoners in India. A Critical analysis.	International of Journal Sociology, Social Anthropology and Social Policy	International	2(1) June 2016 Doi:10.5958/2454-4833.2016.00005.x
83	Role of NGO in Combating Human Trafficking – a critical analysis	JSS Law college Journal	On line	Vol.V Issue I (January-2017 to June 2017) ISSN 2321-4171
84	Supreme Court's observation on working of Competition Commission of India	Bangalore University Law Journal	Referred Journal	ISSN.0973-3280 Vol:6-No.1 January 2016
85	Discharge by Breach in Commercial Contract: in related to Indian Contract law and UK common law system	The Karnataka Law Journal	State	ISSN No. 022-9091 15 th May Part 10
86	A legal analysis of restraint of trade under the Indian Contract Act, 1972 and common law System	The Karnataka Law Journal	State	ISSN No. 022-9091 1 st June, 2017
87	Human rights of women in India- legislative and judicial approach	Noida International University	International	ISSN:2394 vol.2, 2015
88	Extradition is not a rule, will of the states	IJBMS international journal of Business Management and Social science	International	ISSN:2249-7463 Vol.VII, Issue 11(1) August 2017

89	Protection of women against sexual Harassment at workplace: a critical analysis	Karnataka Law journal publication and Seshadripuram Law college Bangalore	State	ISBN: 978-93-80751-71-6 2017
90	Law regime of women in Live-in-relationship- critical analysis	-Do-	State	-Do-
91	Anti-dumping and Competition Law: A critique	International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development	International	ISSN 2349-5979 Vol. 4 Issue 9 Sept.2017
92	De-notified Tribes in India: A legal perspective	International Journal of Legal research and studies	International (on line)	Vol.2. Issue 4, October, 2017
93	Critical evaluation on adoption of Monism for better Governance	Research Arena	National	Vol.5. Issue 7 October 2017
94	Anti-dumping in International Trade: Issues and Perspective	Asian Journal of Development Matters	International	Vol.11 Dec 2017No.2 ISSN:Print:0976-4674
95	Role of Judiciary to ensure Protection for Maintenance rights of senior Citizen in India	International Journal of legal research and studies	International	ISSN:2456-608X Vol.3, Issue1, January-March 2018.
96	Health concern of Street vendors- a case study of Mysore city	Journal of Media and Social Development	National	ISSN 2320-8244 (Print version) 16-17 February 2018 Journal recognized by UGC. Registration No. 64317
97	Health concern of women street vendors – a case study of Karnataka	Asian Journal of Development matters	International	ISSN Print: 0973-9629, ISSN on Line: 0976-4674 UGC approved
98	A socio-legal study of street vendors in Karnataka	Legal Opus SDM Law college Mangalore	College	ISBN:978-93-87072-18-3 Issues No. 11 October 2017

99	Maintenance laws for senior citizen in India-an overview	Self Journal of Social Science	Indian	ISSN: 0975-9999 (P), ISSN on line 2349-1655 UGC approved Journal No. 46622 January-March 2018
100	Dumping and Human Rights Issues	International Journal of Academic Research and Development	International	ISSN(online):2455-4197, Impact factor :RJIF 5.22 UGC approved journal
101	National food security Act in India issues and repercussions.	Karnataka civil and criminal reporter	State	2019(3) KCCR 15 th July 2019
102	Debt bondage: law and enforcing issues	Legal opus	college	ISBN 9789353355616 July 2019
103	Food security in India: a Human rights approach	International Journal of Legal research and studies	International	ISSN:2456-608X Vol 4 issue 3 July-September 2019
104	Interaction and reciprocity of space law and Human rights	Saudi Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences	International	ISSN2415-6256 Print dated 31-10-2019
105	Adoption by a single parents: Issue and Challenges	Al-ameen College of law Journal	College	ISSN:2347-8624 Vol-6 2018-19 October 2019
106	Is extradition Treaty gives social Justice to Injured state? A critical analysis	-Do-	College	-Do-
107	Aftermath the Criminal Law Amendment, 2018	SDM Law college and Centre for Post Graduate studies and Research in law Mangalore.	College	ISBN 978-93087072-16-9 August 2018 issue
108	A critical study of Evolution of Extradition laws in Indian context	International journal of Legal Research and Studies	International (on line)	ISSN:2456-608X Vol-5, Issue i January- March 2020

Ph. D GUIDANCE

- 1) Successfully guided a Ph. D candidate on the thesis entitled "*the problems of refugees in International Law with special reference Indian scenario- a Critical study*", submitted by Sri. Muddaraju. N on 22. March 2011. Ph.D. was awarded to him 22nd March, 2011.
- 2) Successfully guided a Ph.D candidate on the thesis entitled "*A Critical Study of Legal Regime Governing Money Laundering: a Comparative study of International, Iranian and Indian Law*" by Sri. Masood Biranvand an Iranian candidate. Ph.d was awarded to him on 29-11-2011.
- 3) Successfully guided a Ph.D candidate on the thesis entitled "**Domestic application of International Human rights in India**" submitted by Sri. Halashetti Jagadish Sidramappa. And Ph.d was awarded on 10-09-2013.
- 4) Successfully guided a Ph. D candidate on the thesis entitled "**A critical study of working and functioning of Lokayukta in Prevention of corruption in Karnataka**", submitted by D. Rangaswamy and Ph.D was awarded to him on 07-09-2013.
- 5) Successfully guided a Ph.D candidate on the thesis entitled "**A critical Study of Child labour laws and their implementation with special reference to Bangalore city**". Submitted by Smt. Jayasri R Salimath and Ph. D were awarded on 7th January, 2015.
- 6) Successfully guided a Ph.D candidate on the thesis entitled "**A critical study of Legal Control of Anti-Competitive Trade Practises associated with Intellectual Property**". Submitted by Sri. Madivalappa Matolli and awarded to him on 24-01-2015.(Sri. Matolli)
- 7) Successfully guided a Ph.D candidate on the thesis entitled "**International Commercial arbitration: a legal analysis with special reference to the contemporary issues under Indian Law**". Submitted by Saber Habibi SavaKouhi and the same was awarded to him on 08-05-2015.(Habib)
- 8) Successfully guided 8th Ph.D candidate on the thesis entitled "**Transfer Pricing under International Taxation Law with reference to Arms' length Principle** (a comparative Study of India, USA, UK and Australia) and the same was awarded to him on 21st December, 2015. (G.Raghu)
- 9) Successfully guided 9th Ph.d candidate on the topic "*tourism and Environmental pollution: a critical study of laws and policies of India*" and Ph.d. was awarded on 11th April, 2016.(Naveen Chandra)
- 10) Successfully guided 10th Ph.D. candidate on the topic "**Legal Regime of Human Trafficking of women in India- a critical analysis**". And Ph.d was awarded on 22nd June 2017.(smt Valarmathi)
- 11) Successfully guided 11th Ph. D candidate on the topic "**Rights of the Prisoners- a critical analysis**" and the Ph. D was awarded on 21st august, 2017. (Smt. Rashmi)
- 12) Successfully guided 12th Ph.D candidate on the topic " the Law of contracts in commercial transaction: a comparative study in legality of exemption clauses in

- contracts under the India and U.K. Legal regimes and the Ph.D. was awarded on 31st March, 2018.(Sadegh Habibi savadkouhi)
- 13) Successfully guided 13th Ph.D. candidate on the topic “Abuse of dominant Position under competition Act, 2012: A comparative study with U.S.A” the Ph. D was awarded on 7th November, 2018 (Gagan.K)
 - 14) Successfully guided 14th Ph.d candidate on the topic “anti-dumping in International Trade: A legal analysis”. The Ph. D was awarded on 26th September, 2019 and the name of the candidate is “Seyedeh Saeideh Kazemi”.
 - 15) Successfully guided 15th Ph.d candidate on the topic “ a critical analysis of rights of senior citizens with special reference to Mysore district of Karnataka state”. The Ph.d was awarded on 04th November, 2019 and the name of the candidate is “A.R. Prakruthi”.
 - 16) Further, at present 06 more candidates are pursuing their Ph. Ds under my guidance.

SUBJECT EXPERT FOR SELECTION:

1. Invited as selection committee member (BOA member) for the selection of Assistant Professor in the School of Indian Legal thought by the Mahatma Gandhi University Kottayam on 6th February 2012 and participated in the selection process.
2. Invited as selection committee member (BOA member) for the selection of Assistant Professor cum Assistant Director of subject of social science in the Centre for the study of Social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy in Shivaji University Kolhapur and participated in the selection process on 24th September 2012.
3. Nominated and invited to selection committee (as subject expert) for the appointment of Assistant Professor in various law colleges as per Order of the Registrar, Karnataka State Law University, Hubballi (as per the order No. KSLU?acad/Affil/RYS/ESC/2016-17/502. Dated 16/06/2016.
4. Invited as subject expert for the selection of Assistant Professor in law to the Saraswathi law college Chitradurga at the instance of nomination made by the Karnataka State Law University Hubballi and Participated in the selection process as subject expert on 20/06/2016.
5. Invited as subject expert for the selection of Assistant Professor in law to the Vaikunta Baliga College of law, Udupi at the instance of nomination made by the Karnataka State Law University Hubballi and participated in the selection process as subject expert on 30/06/2016.
6. Invited as subject expert for the selection of Assistant Professor in law to the R.V.Biddappa Law College Bidar at the instant of nomination made by the Karnataka State Law University, Hubballi and participated in the selection process as subject expert on 27/07/2016.

7. Invited as subject expert for the selection of Assistant Professor in law to the VSR Law College, Ballari at the instance of nomination made by the Karnataka State Law University, Hubballi, and participated in the selection process as subject expert on 30/08/2016.
8. Invited as subject expert for the selection of Assistant Professor in law to the S.C.A.B Law College Raichur at the instance of nomination made by the Karnataka State Law University, Hubballi, and participated in the selection process as subject expert on 06-10-2016.
9. Invited as subject expert for the selection of assistant professor to senior scale (i.e., extension of AGP) for faculty members of Government Law College Hassan and Government Law College Holenarsipur and participated in the selection process as subject expert on 31-05-2017.
10. Invited as subject expert for the selection of assistant professor to senior scale (i.e., extension of AGP) for faculty members of Government Law College Ramanagar and participated in the selection process as subject expert on 19-06-2017.
11. Invited as subject expert for the selection of assistant professor to senior scale (i.e., extension of AGP) for faculty members of Government Law College Kolar and participated in the selection process as subject expert on 20-06-2017.
12. Invited as University representative of Karnataka State Law University Hubballi as a subject expert to recruit full time faculty for law and economics at Ramaiah Institute of Legal Studies, Bangalore and participated in the selection process so on 26th June 2019.
13. Invited as University representative of Karnataka State Law University Hubballi, as a subject expert to recruit full time faculty of law and pre-legal subjects at Sri.Siddaramaiah Law college, chikkaballapur and participated in selection process on 7th August, 2019.

PARTICIPATION IN SEMINARS AND WORKSHOPS.

1. Participated workshop on “Patent Awareness” conducted by the Department of Studies in Library and Information Science, Karnatak University, Dharwad on 25th August 2003.
2. Attended a workshop on “Copy Right Law” conducted by the SDM Law, college, Mangalore, sponsored by the Ministry of Human Resource Development, New Delhi on 18th October 2003.
3. Successfully coordinated workshop on Intellectual Property Awareness Programme for Police Officers, Artists (Classical, dramatic, painters, craftsman, producers of sound recording and cinematograph, representatives from the Chamber of commerce and industry and librarians, on 8th and 9th January 2005.
4. Participated a workshop on “The Role of Law Colleges Managements in spreading Legal Awareness.” Organised by B.V.Bellad Law College, Belgaum on

17-3-2003.

5. Participated 3 days training programme in Vocational Guidance and Counselling for college teachers conducted by Karnatak University Employment Information and Guidance Bureau from 5-7 April 2005.
6. Participated One Day Symposium on Interdependence of Democracy and Human Rights Organised by Dept of Law, Karnataka University, Dharwad, on 24.3.2005.
7. Successfully coordinated workshop on HIV/ AIDS BILL, 2005 Organised jointly by the University College of Law & Lawyer's Collective, HIV/AIDS Unit, Bangalore, on 4th February 2006. At University College of Law, Dharwad.
8. Participated two User awareness Programme of access to e-Resources of UGC-INFONET DIGITL LIBRARY CONSORTIUM, Organized by Department of Library and Information Science, Manasagangotri, University of Mysore, Mysore, on 21-22 October 2008.
9. Participated two-day National Workshop on "Rooftop Rainwater Harvesting and Ground water Recharge" Organized by Department of Studies in Geology, manasagangotri, University of Mysore, Mysore, on 20th and 21st February, 2009.
10. Participated three days National workshop on 'Samakaleen Hindi Sahitya Ke vividha Aayam' Organized by the Department of Studies in Hindi, Manasagangotri, University of Mysore, Mysore, on 24th, 25th and 26th May 2010.
11. Participated one day conference on "Caste Census: Towards an Inclusive India" Organized by Centre for the Study of Social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy (CSSEIP) National School of India University (NLSUI) Bangalore on 23rd July 2010.
12. Participated one day state Level workshop on Human rights in India (concepts and Issues and Policy) held on 11th April 2011 organized by Department of Studies in Political Science and Public administration, university of Mysore, Mysore.
13. Participated and hosted Suvarna Manasa-2011 exhibition conducted from 15th 24th February, 2011 by the University of Mysore, Mysore as a part of the Golden Jubilee Celebration of the Manasagangotri Campus.
14. Participated two day National Seminar conducted by department of studies in Hindi, Manasagangotri, Mysore on the topic Ajneya Ka sahitya: Punarvichar. Held on 11th and 12th August 2011.
15. Participated in One day state level seminar on "**Problems and Prospectus of Dalit's in Higher Education**" held on 7th October 2011, Organized by Mysore University SC/ST Employees Association (Regd) Mysore.
16. Participated One day National seminar conducted jointly by Babu Jagjivan Ram National foundation and Babu Jagjivan Ram studies, Research and Extension centre on the topic "**Relevance of thoughts of Babu Jagjivan Ram in modern Society**" held on December 16th 2011.
17. Participated in three day ICRC South Indian Regional Teachers' Training Programme on International Humanitarian Law Organized jointly by the Department of studies in law, University of Mysore, Mysore and the International Committe of the Red Cross, Regional Delegation for South Asia, New Delhi during 28-30 May 2012.

18. Participated in the Research methodology Course on Social Exclusion and Discrimination jointly organized by the Indian Institute of Dalith Studies, New Delhi and Centre for the Study of social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy, NLSIU, Bangalore from 31st May to 02 June, 2012 at the International Training centre, NLSIU campus.
19. Participated in one day State level Training Workshop on “ Human Rights and Social Exclusion” conducted by Centre for the Study of social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy (CSSEIP) and National Human Rights commission, New Delhi on 15th December, 2012.
20. Participated in 11 day National Workshop on Advanced Research Methodology in Social Sciences from 16th January to 26th January, 2013. This workshop was organized by CSSEIP, university of Mysore and sponsored by ICSSR New Delhi.
21. Participated in two day National Conference on “Inclusive Development of Marginalized Groups in Contemporary India: issues and challenges on 27th and 28th 2013. This conference was organized by CSSEIP, university of Mysore, Mysore.
22. Participated in two day National CME workshop on New Public Health Issues in India. The workshop was organized on 27th and 28th December, 2013 by CSSEIP and this workshop was sponsored by National Academy of Medical Sciences (India).
23. Participated in the two day conference conducted by the SDM Institute for Management Development on 13th and 14th November, 2014. The topic of conference was “Corporate Social Responsibility”
24. Participated in one day workshop titled “technology in Higher education” organized by University of Mysore in association with Karnataka Gnana Aayoga on 7th February, 2015.
25. Participated in two day National Workshop on “interface between politics and Development: India after Independence”. This workshop was jointly organized by Department of Political Science and University with potential for Excellence Project, Focus Area-II on 14th and 15th September, 2015.
26. Participated in the two day National Workshop on “New Human Development Index for Tribal Health Care” conducted by Centre for the Study of Social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy (CSSEIP), University of Mysore, Mysore on 30th and 31st October, 2015.
27. Participated in one day basic training programme on Human rights (sponsored by national Human Rights Commission, New Delhi), on 7th November, 2015. The seminar was conducted by JSS Law College Mysore.
28. Participated in 5 day Indian Science Congress, from 3rd to 7th January 2016, organized jointly by the Indian Science Congress and University of Mysore.
29. Participated in one day “Model United Nations conference” 2017 conducted by Department of studies in law, university of Mysore, Mysore, on 27th March, 2017.

30. Participated in one day workshop on “prevention of cruelty to animals” conducted jointly by National Law School of India University Bangalore and JSS Law college, Mysure on 28th April, 2017.

REFRESHER COURSES ATTENDED

1. Attended a refresher course conducted by the Department of Studies in Law, Nagarjuna University, Andhra Pradesh held during 9th Feb to 2nd March 1998.
2. Attended a refresher course conducted by the CEERA, National Law School of India University Bangalore held during 22nd October to 11th Nov 1998.

RESPONSIBILITIES UNDER TAKEN AT THE COLLEGE LEVEL:

- Faculty Coordinator: Legal Service Authorities activities during the academic year 1999-2000, University College of Law, Dharwad, Karnataka University, Dharwad.
- Closely Associated with National Moot Court Competitions and in SC Javali National Moot Court Competition since 1999, University College of Law, Dharwad, Karnataka University, and Dharwad.
- Member College Governing Council body, University College of Law, Dharwad, Karnataka University, Dharwad.
- Member College and Hostel Admission Committee, University College of Law, Dharwad, Karnataka University, Dharwad.

CHAIRMAN

- Serving as Chairman of Board of studies in Law for both UG and PG.
- Serving as Chairman of Board of Examiners in KSOU Law Department, MGM, MYSORE. (No. KSOU/Ex-cw-01/BOE/2011-12 dated 14-06-12)

DISTINCTIVE ACHIVEMENT:

I have the honour of drafting a Bill “*Karnataka Rural Employment Guarantee Bill 2005*” in response to the request made by the Ministry of Law and Parliament Affairs, Government of Karnataka, Karnataka. A copy of the draft bill and certificate issued by the competent authority is enclosed for kind consideration.

Visiting Faculty.

- Visiting faculty to Police Training College, Mysore,
- Academic Staff College, University of Mysore, Mysore.
- Academic staff college, Karnataka University Dharawad
- Invited faculty to the Administrative Training Institute, Mysore

Lecture Delivered.

1. Delivered lecture on the topic **Indian Constitution** from 18-01-2013 to 09-01-2013 at the Govt C.P.C Polytechnic College Mysore.
2. Delivered lecture on the topic **Human rights and UNO** from 21-08-2013 at the Govt C.P.C Polytechnic college Kushalnagar.
3. Delivered lecture on the topic **Babu Jagjivan Ram and Personality** from 12th and 13th August 2014 at Babu Jagjivan Ram studies, Research and Extension Centre.
4. Delivered lecture on the topic **Indian Constitution** from 01-07-2013 – 05-07-2013 at KSOU, Dr. Ambedkar studies, Research and Extension Centre.
5. Delivered 14 lectures on various law topics at the UGC Academic staff college from 15-05-2010 to 27-08-2014.
6. Delivered a lecture on the topic “**Refugees and Human Rights**” in the 12th Refresher course held at UGC-Human resource Development centre, University of Mysore, Mysore on 17th November, 2015.
7. Delivered a lecture on the topic “**Judicial contribution for the Protection of Human Rights**” in the 12th Refresher Course held at UGC-Human resource Development centre, University of Mysore, Mysore on 22nd November, 2015.
8. Delivered a lecture on the topic “grievance redressal: Needs and methods” in the 6th Non-teaching staff training Programme conducted by the UGC Human Resource Development Centre on 2nd June 2016. The thrust area of Programme “understood the change in the Knowledge Universe”.
9. Delivered a lecture as a resource person to the participants of 110th Orientation Programme organized by UGC-Human Resource Development centre, University of Mysore, Mysore, on 9th August 2016.
10. Delivered a lecture as a resource person to the participants of 112th Orientation Programme organized by UGC-Human Resource Development centre, University of Mysore, Mysore, on 23rd December 2016.

11. Delivered two lectures as a resource person to the participants of 3rd Winter Programme (Refresher course in Human rights) organized by the UGC-Human Resource Development Centre, University of Mysore, Mysore, on 30th and 31st December, 2016.
12. Delivered a lecture as a resource person in the orientation programme conducted by Human Resource Development Centre, Karnataka University Dharwad on 21st February 2017 on the topic *legal status of refugees*.
13. Delivered a lecture as a resource person in the orientation programme conducted by Human Resource Development Centre, Karnataka University Dharwad on 21st February 2017 on the topic “Socio –economic and legal status of single women”.
14. Delivered a two lecture on 17th May, 2017 as a resource person in the Administrative Training Institute, Mysore to the class I and II officer on the topic “Liability of state in Tort and Liability of state in Contract, privileges and Immunities of the State in suits” .
15. Moderated one seminar session as Resource Person to the Participants of 114th Orientation Programme organized by the UGC-Human Resource Development Centre, University of Mysore on 6th January, 2018.
16. Delivered a lecture as resource person on 23rd January 2018 at the 1st Refresher Course in Political Science and Public administration Assistant Professor. The Refresher Course was organized by UGC-Human Resource Development centre, University of Mysore.
17. Delivered a lecture on 22nd January, 2018 as a resource person in the UGC-Human Resource Development Centre to the 1st refresher course to the Assistant Professors of Political Science and Public Administration.
18. Delivered a lecture on the topic “**World Trade Organization**” on 3rd August, 2018 in the 68th Orientation Programme conducted by UGC- Human resource Development Centre, Karnatak University Dharawad.
19. Delivered a lecture on the topic “**Dispute settlement body under WTO**” on 3rd August, 2018 in the 68th Orientation Programme conducted by UGC- Human resource Development Centre, Karnataka University Dharawad.
20. Delivered a lecture on the topic “one Nation one Constitution” at sarada vilas law college, Mysore on 26th November, 2019.
21. Delivered a lecture on the topic “**Socio-economic and Legal study on single women**” on 2nd January 2020 in the refresher course Programme conducted by UGC- Human resource Development Centre, Bangalore University Bangalore. The thrust area of programme was “ Human rights for vulnerable groups: Law and Perspective”.

22. Invited to deliver a lecture on the topic “one Nation one constitution” as a subject expert on 26th November, 2019, at Sarada vilas Law college, Mysore.
- 23.

Organization of Seminars/conference/workshops.

- Organized **one** day National Seminar on “Constitutional Status of Religious Conversion” on 26th February, 2009. This seminar was sponsored by the University of Mysore, Mysore.
- Successfully coordinated workshop on Intellectual Property Awareness Programme for Police Officers, Artists (Classical, dramatic, painters, craftsman, producers of sound recording and cinematograph, representatives from the Chamber of commerce and industry and librarians, on 8th and 9th January 2005, at University College of Dharwad.
- Successfully coordinated workshop on HIV/ AIDS BILL, 2005 Organised jointly by the University College of Law & Lawyer’s Collective, HIV/AIDS Unit, Bangalore, on 4th February 2006. At University College of Law, Dharwad.
- Successfully coordinated an Orientation Course for political science and law teachers on the topic “human rights” conducted by Academic Staff College sponsored by University Grants Commission.
- Successfully conducted one day Prelude Conference jointly with Indian Institute of Public Administration and Dr.B.R.Ambedkar Research and Extension Centre on the topic “**Reservation and Inclusive Growth**” on 13th October, 2010.
- Successfully conducted a seminar on the topic “Violence against women” in collaboration with Department of Social work, Department of Women studies, Department of sociology and an NGO called, “Ashodaya” on 25th November 2010 at EMMRC Building Manasagangotri, Mysore. This seminar coincidentally on “**violence against women day**” as declared by United Nations.
- Successfully conducted two day National conference on “**Ethno historical Development of De-notified tribes: problems and Prospects**” on 23rd and 24th December 2010 at BIMS University of Mysore, Mysore. This conference was partially funded by Indian Council of Historical Research.
- Successfully organized and conducted Two Day National Conference on “**Women and Work: towards economic inclusion**” on 21st and 22nd March, 2011, at EMMRC building, University of Mysore, Manasagangotri, Mysore: this conference was organized jointly by CSSEIP and Women study centre, University of Mysore, Mysore.
- Successfully conducted and organized one day state level symposium on 27th March, 2011, on the topic “**Dr.B.R. Ambedkar views on Social Exclusion and Inclusion**” at Ambedkar Research and Extension Centre, Manasagangotri, Mysore.
- Successfully conducted and organized two day National conference on 8th and 9th September 2011 on the topic “**Multilevel Interventions for Health Care: framing New Inclusive Policies**” at BIMS. This conference was partially funded by Indian council for Medical Research.

- Successfully conducted and organized two day National Conference on ‘**Regional imbalance, banking Industry and Inclusive growth- a focus on 12th Five Year Plan**’ sponsored by National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD), Karnataka held on 15th and 16th December 2011 at EMMRC, Auditorium, Manasagongotri, Mysore.
- Successfully Conducted for State Level seminar on “**Missing Girls and Women: Issues and Implications**”, funded by Karnataka State Commission for Women, Government of Karnataka, at University of Mysore on 23rd and 24th January 2012.
- Successfully conducted and organized two day National Policy conference on “**Social Exclusion, Development and Autonomy Movements**” partially funded by ICSSR New Delhi, and the conference held on 22nd and 23rd August, 2012 at EMMRC, auditorium manasagangotri, Mysore.
- Successfully conducted for National Conference on “**Financial Inclusion in India: Issues and Challenges**”, funded by ICSSR, New Delhi, at University of Mysore on 09th and 10th October 2012
- Successfully conducted for State Level Workshop on “**Human Rights and Social Exclusion**”, , funded by National Human Rights Commission, New Delhi at University of Mysore on 15th December, 2012.
- Successfully conducted for **Workshop Convener National Workshop on “Advanced Research Methodology in Social Sciences**”, funded by ICSSR, New Delhi held on January 16th – 27th 2013, held at University of Mysore, Mysore.
- Successfully conducted for **National Conference on “Inclusive Agriculture Growth India: Issues and Challenges**”, funded by ICSSR, Hyderabad, held on January 30th – 31st 2013, held at University of Mysore, Mysore.
- Successfully conducted for National Conference on “**Inclusive Higher Education and Marginalized Sections: Dynamics and Discourses**”, funded by ICSSR, New Delhi, held on 1st and 2nd August 2013, held at University of Mysore, Mysore.
- Successfully conducted for National Conference on “**Inclusive Development of Marginalized Groups in Contemporary India: Issues And Challenges**”, funded by University of Mysore, held on 27th and 28th September 2013, held at University of Mysore, Mysore.
- Successfully conducted_for National Conference on “**Social Exclusion and Reservation Policy in India: New Debates**”, funded by ICSSR, Hyderabad, held on 1st and 2nd 2013, held at University of Mysore, Mysore.
- Successfully conducted for National Workshop on “**New Public Health Issues in India, funded by National Academy of Medical Sciences (NAMS)**, New Delhi, held on December 27th – 28th 2013, held at University of Mysore, Mysore.
- Successfully conducted for National workshop on “**Developments in Statistical Methods for Data Analysis of Excluded Groups**” sponsored by Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, New Delhi, held on 20th and 21st March 2013, held at University of Mysore, Mysore.
- Successfully conducted for National workshop on “**Developments in Statistical Methods for Data Analysis of Excluded Groups**” sponsored by Ministry of

Statistics and Programme Implementation, New Delhi, held on 20th and 21st March 2013, held at University of Mysore, Mysore

- Successfully conducted for National Conference on “**Rural Development and Inclusive Growth: New Debates**” funded by ICSSR, New Delhi held on 21st and 22nd August 2014 at University of Mysore, Mysore.
- Successfully coordinated 12th Refresher Course in Human Rights during 6th November, 2015 to 26th November, 2015 conducted by UGC- Human Resource Development Centre, University of Mysore, and Mysore. The thrust area of Refresher course was “**Human Rights of vulnerable Sections of the Society- A Discourse**”.
- Successfully coordinated three day National workshop on “Legal Research Methodology” conducted by the Department of studies and research in law, University of Mysore, during 6th, 7th and 8th February 2020.

Paper settings

- Paper setter for K.P.S.C examination
- Paper setter for K-SET examination.

Investigative Report:

1. On socio economic survey of **Handi Jogi’s in Mysore District. 2012**
2. On socio economic conditions of **Pourakarmika’s in Karnataka-A case study of Mysore District.2012**

List of Research Projects

SL.No.	Title	Funding agency	Total Budget (in Rupees)	Year	Remarks/status
1.	Issues and Concerns of Missing girls in Karnataka- a case study of Mysore district. (Project Director)	Karnataka State Women’s Commission, Government of Karnataka	Rs.100,000	2011	Completed
2	Media and social Development: A case study of Karnataka (Project committee Member)	UGC/UPE-FA-II	50 lakhs	2012	Under Progress
3	Extending financial assistance to SC/ST Nursing Students studying in various schools and colleges	Govt. Of Karnataka	4,56,000	2012	Completed

	other than government Schools/colleges (Project Director)				
4	A study on situation analysis of children in Mysore district. (Project Director)	Dept. Of Women and Child Development, Government of Karnataka and UNICEF	Rs.3,58,000/-	2011	Completed.
5	An empirical analysis of old age homes in Karnataka. (Principal Investigator)	UGC, New Delhi	Rs. 3,99,800	2012	completed
6	Socio-Economic and legal Status of street Vendors: A case Study of Karnataka	ICSSR New Delhi	Rs.4,80,000	2016	completed

Instructional design and delivery of prescribed material (self learning kit etc.).

1. A module has been prepared on the topic **Trade secrets** (under Intellectual Property laws) a course offered by Karnataka State Open University, Mysore, in the year 2009-10 (Total 8 Units)
2. A module has been prepared Ambedkar studies Research and extension centre, Karnataka State Open University, Mysore for the year 2010-11.(Total 15 Units)
3. A Module has been prepared on the topic **“Administrative Law”** a course offered by Karnataka State Open University, Mysore in the year 2014.(Total 20 Units)

Publication of books:

1. Co-edited a book entitled **“India Development: Issues and Prospectives”** Published by Anmol Publications Pvt.Ltd NewDelhi-110 002 (India) ISBN. No. 978-81-261-4624-6/2011.
2. Published an edited volume entitled **“Denotified tribes in India- A Relook”** published by Lap Lambert Academic Publishing, Germany, ISBN NO. 978-3-8465-5882-9 in 2011.
3. Published an edited book entitled **“Dictionary of intellectual property law terms”**. This book is published by Prasaranga, University of Mysore, Mysore. ISBN-13 978-81-921217-0-3.2013

4. Published an edited book entitled **“Financial Inclusion in India: issues and challenges” (2013)**
5. Edited and published a book **“Inclusive Agricultural Growth in India: issues and challenges. (2013)**
6. **Higher Education: between quality and Reservation. (Co-author)** Kalpaz publication Delhi ISBN: 978-81-212-1182-6(2014)
7. **Rural development and Inclusive Growth: linkage Implications** (co-author) Kalpaz Publication Delhi. ISBN No. 978-93-5128-100-9 (2015)
8. **Constitutional status of religious conversions in India: serials Publication Delhi. ISBN NO. 978-81-8387-766-4 (2016).**
9. **Latin kanoonu sutragalu mattu padagala Nigantu: published by Kuvempu Bhasha bharathi Pradikara Bangalore-560056 (2016).**

Ph.d Evaluation:

1. Evaluated a thesis of Shri. Vishnuprasad. R on the topic “ a critical study of Judicial incorporation of international Human rights into the Indian Legal system.
2. Evaluated a thesis of Smt. Baig. S.N.S on the topic **“efficiency of Dispute Resolution under Industrial Dispute Act, 1947** with special emphasis on conciliation.(3rd December 2016)
3. Evaluated a thesis of Smt. Uma Devi R. Hire math on the topic **“Critical Evaluation of Law relating to victim compensation in India”**. (17th Jan 2017).
4. Evaluated a thesis of Ms. Sandhy Ram on the topic **“rights of older persons- A socio legal study in the state of Goa and state of Kerala”** (2nd 12 2016).
5. Evaluated a thesis of Sri. Ganesh P. Hegde on the topic **“Judicial Contribution towards Protection of Environmental Rights”** a critical study. (1st Feb 2018).
6. Evaluated a thesis of Smt. Jyothi Gugupadappa on the topic **“Implementation of Food adulteration Act, 1954- a critical study with special reference of Gulbarga revenue division”**.(29th July, 2019).
7. Evaluated a thesis of G.S Kishen on the topic **“Changing Indian Judicial response towards administrative decisions- a comparative U.S.A and U.K”** (12th July 2019).
8. Evaluated a thesis of Bijoy M.S.Raj on the topic **“Implementation of labour laws in the IT sector as SEZ- with special reference to IT employees in techno park”** the thesis was guided by Dr.Sindu Thulaseedharan (18th February, 2020).

Local Inquiry Committee:

1. Nominated and Served as Local Inquiry committee for inspection of six law colleges in Bangalore from 19th to 22nd November, 2018.

Membership to International Organisation/journals

- 1) Member of Editorial Board to International Journal of Social and Economic Research.

- 2) Member of Editorial Board to Asian Journal of Development Matters.
- 3) Member to SAARC Forum of Social Scientist
- 4) Member to editorial board to “Journal of commerce Management Journal of Law Journal of education” .
- 5) Member of Editorial committee to “Journal of commerce, Management, and Journal of Law Journal of Education.

Dr. Ramesh